

Mental Health as a Predictor of the Probability of Recidivism among Indian Convicts

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The present study evaluated the link between mental health and the probability of recidivism amongst Indian convicts. The sample consisted of 200 convicts from Tihar Prisons, New Delhi. The assessment of mental health and the probability of recidivism was done using the Mental Health Continuum-Short Form (MHC-SF) and the Criminal Sentiments Scale-Modified (CSS-M). Scales were translated into Hindi using the backward-translation approach. Data analyses were done using Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient analysis, which indicated a significant negative correlation between mental health and the probability of recidivism ($r = -.40, p < .01$). Furthermore, simple linear regression analysis indicated that mental health significantly predicted recidivism ($\beta = -.40, p < .001$), accounting for 16% of the variance. The results of the present research highlight that adverse mental health is strongly linked with an elevated risk of recidivism. Therefore, significant implications highlighted in the study are the rising importance of combining mental health initiatives within prison settings to increase rehabilitation and actively reduce recidivism.

Keywords: Mental health, recidivism, prison inmates, rehabilitation, Indian convicts

Correctional institutions tend to leave a lasting impression on the well-being of an incarcerated individual (Moran, 2014). A growing body of research indicates that the mental well-being of prison inmates during incarceration has a crucial role in shaping their post-release behaviour. Whether favourable or compromised, it influences their reintegration into the community as well as their likelihood of reoffending. Research further indicates that mental health concerns, including conduct disorders, substance dependence, and psychotic symptoms, can be significant predictors of heightened risk of recidivism (Bonta et al., 2014; Fazel & Yu, 2011). Furthermore, convicts persistently show heightened risk of psychiatric symptoms such as symptoms of depression, anxiety, psychosis, disorders related to personality, etc. (Baranyi et al., 2019; Fazel & Seewald, 2012; Weber et al., 2022).

Deteriorating mental health can undermine rehabilitation efforts within correctional settings, thereby increasing the likelihood of recidivism. Moreover, empirical evidence suggests that recidivism can be reduced by tailoring structured psychosocial interventions aimed at facilitating the emotional regulation, coping strategies and social functioning of the incarcerated individuals (Morgan et al., 2012; McIntosh et al., 2021). It must be taken into account that the mental health of convicts could be fragile at the time of imprisonment; it becomes essential to address and manage the

psychological concerns during incarceration. This can be done by the implementation of structured and pre-planned daily routines, the integration of accessible mental health amenities in the prison premises, and targeted rehabilitative support (Hassan et al., 2011; Dirkzwager & Nieuwebeerta, 2018). Research suggests that despite continued efforts to improve mental health within the prison, uniform improvement is not necessary, largely due to diverse intersectional differences among convicts, such as age, previous debts, prior psychiatric diagnosis, etc. (Weber et al., 2022). These sociodemographic and psychological aspects play a crucial role in determining persistent distress, improvement among convicts during their period of imprisonment, and in structured correctional planning.

Additionally, a marked effect of mental health on the likelihood of reoffending can also be understood with various theoretical models. One of the models is General Strain Theory (Agnew, 1992) which indicates that people enduring heightened psychological distress are more likely to indulge in delinquent behaviours as a means of coping mechanisms. In the prison context, challenges associated with imprisonment become difficult to manage when convicts experience persistent psychological distress, lack of emotional regulation, feelings of hopelessness and helplessness, etc. This psychological distress can negatively impact problem-focused coping and adaptive decision-making skills among convicts and thereby increase the likelihood of reoffending.

Another theoretical evidence comes from the Risk-Need-Responsivity Theory (Andrews et al., 1990) suggesting that focus of the rehabilitation policies within correctional institutions ought to address criminogenic needs of the convicts, such as psychological capabilities and emotional functionality, to promote adaptive behavioural change and facilitate their successful reintegration into society. According to this model, mental health concerns that have been left unaddressed become major contributors to risk factors that heighten the possibility of persistent criminal behaviour and reoffending.

Additionally, sociological perspectives in understanding

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mental health and imprisonment are the Importation Theory (Irwin & Cressey, 1962) and the Deprivation Theory (Sykes, 1958, 2007). The importation theory indicates that convicts may come with preconceived vulnerabilities, which make them susceptible to incarceration and their well-being within prison. Conversely, the deprivation model indicates and supports the idea that psychological distress is increased by the prison environment due to various prison-based stressors, such as lack of autonomy and constrained social and emotional connections. Therefore, the importation theory and the deprivation theory argue that a multifaceted interaction exists between pre-existing psychological vulnerabilities based on the convict's social environment and the prison-based stressors and conditions of imprisonment.

Most of the current literature pertains to the Western correctional institutions, and there is a gap in the literature in the Indian context. Hence, the current study evaluated mental health in the Indian prison context based on the notion that mental health can be both cause and consequence (Defoe et al., 2013; Reising et al., 2018) of delinquent behaviour. Considering India's unique socio-demographic variability, diverse cultural background, varying prison environments across the country, etc., it is crucial to address this empirical gap to have evidence-based rehabilitation policies. Thus, the present study aims to understand the link that exists between the mental health of Indian convicts and their probability of reoffending.

Hypotheses of the Study

- *H1*: There would be an inverse relationship between mental health and the probability of recidivism among convicts.
- *H2*: Mental health would significantly predict the probability of recidivism among convicts.

Method

Participants

Participants for the current investigation were taken from Tihar Prisons, New Delhi, which housed approximately 20,000 inmates across nine jails, as of December 2024. The study participants were drawn from two jails within the prison compound exclusively designated for convicted inmates. Participants were considered eligible for inclusion in the study if they had served a minimum of six months of their jail sentence, were housed under a general prison regime (i.e., not under disciplinary or psychiatric segregation), and provided informed consent. Furthermore, it was ensured that the convicts possessed sufficient language comprehension. The final study sample comprised 200 convicts aged between 24 and 54 years ($M = 38.43$ years & $SD = 7.23$), with prison sentences ranging from 1 year to life imprisonment. The socio-demographic and criminological characteristics of the participants are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Percentage (%) and Frequency (n) Distribution of Participants' Socio-demographic Variables and Criminological Characteristics

Characteristics	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Sex		
Male	185	93%
Female	15	8%
Marital Status		
Unmarried	68	34%

Married	114	57%
Divorced	8	4%
Separated	4	2%
Widowed	6	3%
Family Type		
Nuclear	102	51%
Joint	88	44%
Extended	10	5%
Highest Educational Level		
Primary School	5	3%
Middle School	48	24%
Secondary School	49	25%
Senior Secondary School	30	15%
Graduation	21	11%
Post-graduation	7	4%
Uneducated	40	20%
Occupation prior to Conviction		
Self-Employed	96	48%
Government Service	9	5%
Private Service	73	37%
Unemployed	22	11%
Type of Offence		
Offence against Human Body	150	75%
Offence against Property	41	21%
Offence against State and Terrorism	9	5%
Crime Serving		
1 Offence	20	10%
2 or More Offences	180	90%
Duration of Sentence		
Up to 10 years	63	32%
Up to 20 years	1	1%
Life Imprisonment	136	68%
Previous Jail Sentence		
Served	25	12.5%
Not Served	175	87.5%

Note. $N = 200$ (n is for each condition). The average age of participants was 38.43 years ($SD = 7.23$)

Ethical Consideration

The present research complied with the ethical standards of the American Psychological Association (APA), Declaration of Helsinki (2013) and was approved by the host institution's Ethics Committee as well as the authorities from Tihar Jail, New Delhi, India. The confidentiality of the participants was ensured by anonymising all data during analyses and maintaining strict confidentiality procedures.

Measures

Demographic Information Questionnaire: The socio-demographic information of the participants, such as age, education, nationality, occupation, marital status, duration of incarceration, history of imprisonment, and type of crime, was collected by using a self-reporting demographic information questionnaire.

Mental Health Continuum-Short Form (MHC-SF; Keyes, 2009): Mental health was measured using the Mental Health Continuum-Short Form. To ensure participants' language comprehension, the instrument was translated into Hindi. The Hindi version of Mental Health Continuum-Short Form (MHC-SF-HV) retained the original 14-item structure of the English MHC-SF (Keyes, 2009). The MHC-

SF is a self-report instrument that assesses individuals' mental health experiences over past month, using a six-point Likert scale ranging from "never" to "every day". The instrument measures three core components of positive mental health, namely, emotional well-being, social well-being, and psychological well-being. The instrument has shown robust psychometric qualities, with high discriminant validity and internal consistency greater than .80 across both adolescent and adult populations.

Criminal Sentiments Scale-Modified (CSS-M; Shields & Simourd, 1991): The probability of recidivism was evaluated using the Criminal Sentiments Scale-Modified. To ensure participants' language comprehension, the instrument was translated into Hindi. The Hindi Version Criminal Sentiments Scale-Modified (CSS-M-HV) retained the original 41-item structure of the English CSS-M (Shields & Simourd, 1991). CSS-M is a self-report instrument measured on a three-point Likert scale and has 3 domains, namely, Law-Court-Police (LCP), Tolerance with Law Violations (TLV) and Identification with Criminal Others (ICO). Higher scores on the CSS-M indicate stronger deviant attitudes. Empirical evidence has suggested that higher scores on CSS-M are predictive of an increased likelihood of reoffending among violent offenders (Simourd & van de Ven, 1999). The instrument has demonstrated strong reliability with Cronbach's alpha ranging from .75 to .94 for the overall scale.

Procedure

The Mental Health Continuum-Short Form (MHC-SF) and Criminal Sentiments Scale-Modified (CSS-M) were adapted and translated into Hindi in accordance with the backward-translation procedure to ensure semantic and contextual equality (Hambleton, 2004). Data were collected through paper-and-pencil surveys administered to groups of 5-7 convicts, with each session lasting approximately 40 minutes. Participation in the study was voluntary, and rigorous confidentiality regulations were implemented. Participants were assured their responses would not affect their lives within prison or their legal standing, that data would be gathered with their informed written consent, and that their personal information would remain anonymous using randomly allocated identification numbers. Before the beginning of the session, the investigator explained the objectives of the research and read aloud the informed consent form. Participants were also provided with precise instructions for the completion of the questionnaires. No monetary incentives were offered.

Data Analysis

IBM SPSS Statistics (Version 22) was used to analyse the data. Simple linear regression was used to analyse the relationship between mental health and the probability of recidivism.

Results

The aim of the study was to explore the relationship between mental health and the probability of recidivism among 200 Indian convicts.

The descriptive statistics and Pearson product-moment correlations among the study variables are presented in Table 2. The mean score for mental health was $M = 35.17$ ($SD = 15.25$), whereas the mean score for probability of recidivism was $M = 39.15$ ($SD = 10.72$). Pearson correlation analysis showed a significant negative association between mental health and the probability of recidivism ($r = -.40, p < .01$), indicating that better mental health was associated

with a low probability of reoffending.

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics and Correlation between Mental Health (MHC-SF-HV) and Probability of Recidivism (CSS-M-HV)

Variable	M	SD	1	2
1. Mental Health	35.17	15.25	-	
2. Probability of Recidivism	39.15	10.72	-.40**	-

Note. $N = 200$. Values represent Pearson correlation coefficients. ** $p < .01$.

Table 3

Simple Linear Regression Predicting Probability of Recidivism (CSS-M-HV) from Mental Health (MHC-SF-HV)

Predictor	B	SE	β	t	p
Constant	48.96	1.76	-	27.85	<.001
Mental Health	-0.28	0.05	-.40	-6.08	<.001

Note. $N = 200$. Dependent variable = Probability of recidivism (CSS-M-HV). $R = .40, R^2 = .16$, Adjusted $R^2 = .15, F(1, 198) = 36.98, p < .001$.

To further examine whether mental health predicted the probability of recidivism, a simple linear regression analysis was conducted. The results showed a statistically significant relationship, $F(1, 198) = 36.98, p < .001$, explaining 16% of the variance in probability of recidivism ($R^2 = .16$). Mental health appeared as a significantly negative predictor of probability of recidivism ($\beta = -.40, t = -6.08, p < .001$), which implies that lower scores on mental health were linked with higher scores on the probability of recidivism scale.

These findings indicate that psychological well-being plays a crucial role in determining inmates' attitudes and dispositions related to the likelihood of reoffending.

Discussion

The focus of the current investigation was to evaluate the relationship between mental health and the probability of recidivism among Indian convicts. The results highlighted a significant negative correlation between mental health and the probability of recidivism, signifying a strong relation between poorer mental health and a higher probability of recidivism among convicts. The results of correlational analysis indicated a moderate level of negative correlation between mental health and the probability of recidivism, signifying that poor mental health leads to a higher probability of recidivism. Further analysis through regression also demonstrated that a significant predictor of the probability of recidivism was mental health, implying that convicts' overall well-being is a significant contributor in convicts' likelihood of reoffending. Poor mental health might lead to a lack of healthy coping mechanisms, such as problem-focused coping and adequate decision-making capability, a lack of emotional regulation, etc. This level of inadequacy in terms of coping with prison-based stressors may lead to a high risk of engaging in delinquent behaviours, thereby elevating the risk of recidivism (Agnew, 1992, 2001, 2006; Seyidoğlu, 2024). Hence, the results of the current research support the hypotheses and highlight the dire significance of mental health in shaping convicts' behaviour in prison as well as their post-release outcomes.

Additionally, mental health in the present study has been conceptualised as a multidimensional construct that comprises

emotional, psychological, and social well-being. Any negative impact on these three dimensions of well-being may lead to difficulties with emotional regulation, interpersonal interactions and coping mechanisms. Such psychological difficulties further lead to difficult experiences in handling stressors and, as a consequence, increase the possibility of reoffending and involvement in delinquent activities.

The present findings are especially relevant within the context of convicts incarcerated in Tihar Jail. Tihar houses convicts from diverse backgrounds in the context of sociodemographic status, varied psychological backgrounds, etc. By definition, prisons curtail the personal autonomy and liberty of an individual as part of the mandate of the criminal justice system that is aimed towards accountability, behavioural modification and gradual reintegration into society. While correctional institutions are intended to reform and facilitate rehabilitation, the incarcerated individuals may experience powerlessness, loneliness, lack of social support, isolation, alienation, separation from significant others, uncertainty about the future, and difficulty in adapting to the significant regime of the prison environment. Such negative experiences can increase psychological discomfort, prolonged stress, emotional trauma, withdrawal from social engagement and further exacerbate the likelihood of reoffending (Albertie et al., 2017; Chassay & Kremer, 2022; Crewe et al., 2017; Favril & Van Ginneken, 2023; Listwan et al., 2013; Molleman & Van Ginneken, 2015; Windzio, 2006).

Furthermore, the findings are consistent with empirical evidence emphasising the impact of mental health on the probability of reoffending. Reising et al. (2018) highlighted that individuals experiencing symptoms of depression and anxiety are more likely to engage in repeated reoffending and continued involvement in crimes. Similarly, Wallace and Wang (2020) emphasised that flourishing mental health during the period of imprisonment showed signs of betterment in post-release psychological well-being and reduced likelihood of reoffending. Furthermore, Semenza and Grosholz (2019) in their study suggested that increased levels of misconduct during the imprisonment were linked with inmates' mental and physical health concerns, where deteriorated mental and physical health could worsen the misconduct and increase maladaptive behaviours. Similarly, Edgemon and Clay-Warner (2019) in their study of 214 state prisons found that deteriorating mental health among inmates showed a strong association with heightened misconduct in the prison and a high risk of failed post-release reintegration into society. In conclusion, empirical evidence supports and reinforces the results of the present research, indicating that deteriorated mental health is a risk factor that shows a significant relationship with heightened probability of recidivism.

These findings collectively point towards the significance of integrating mental health with the environment within the prison as a key component for rehabilitation practices and reducing the risk of recidivism.

Limitations and Implications of the Study

Although the present study contributes in bridging the research gap in the field, certain limitations warrant acknowledgement. First, the utilisation of self-report measures to evaluate mental health and the probability of recidivism. Relying on self-report data solely may lead to biases in response, socially desirable responses, etc. Second, longitudinal research is needed to establish whether better mental

health during the period of incarceration is required to reduce reoffending behaviours. Finally, the sample inclusion from solely Tihar Jail makes it difficult to generalise the results to other correctional institutions within India that might vary in the context of different sample characteristics, resources available in different correctional institutions, etc.

Despite acknowledging the limitations, the present research proposes important implications for correctional policies and rehabilitation initiatives. The major highlight of the findings is acknowledging the importance of mental health as a protective factor against reoffending. Integrating well-planned, structured psychological assistance and effective counselling techniques into rehabilitation initiatives in the prison. An increase in access to mental health facilities within prison settings may help improve convicts' emotional well-being, learn emotional regulation, learn healthy coping mechanisms, etc. Such effective prison-based interventions may help in acknowledging vulnerabilities that significantly heighten the possibility of recidivism.

Conclusion

The present research evaluated the relationship between mental health and the probability of recidivism among Indian convicts. The results highlighted a significant negative relationship between mental health and the probability of recidivism, indicating that poorer mental health is linked with a higher likelihood of reoffending risk among convicts. The present research contributes to the limited empirical research evaluating mental health within the Indian context and emphasises the need to address mental health within correctional settings. Expanding mental health assistance within correctional institutions may help the convicts to improve their quality of life by improving their mental health during incarceration, along with reducing the risk of recidivism post-release. Hence, acknowledging and working towards the mental health requirements of convicts is a significant step towards functional rehabilitation initiatives and further increasing chances of effective reintegration of the convicts into the society for a better future.

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